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Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF ANEMIA INCIDENCE DURING LABOR OF
ACTIVE STAGE**¹Mahzaib Shafqat, ²Khalid Hussain, ³Aitzaz Ahmad¹Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore.²Wah Medical College, Wah Cantt.³The University Of Lahore, Lahore.

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Abstract:

Objective: This research's key focus was on the prevention of anaemia in pregnant women between the ages of 18-42 by simple tests such as CBC.

Place and Duration: This research was carried out from January 2019 to March 2019 over three months in Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

Materials and Methods: The research design was a cross-sectional observational model in which 500 pregnant women were included in the Lahore Tertiary Care Hospitals study. The method of Systematic Random Sampling was introduced. Using SPSS version 20, the data was analysed.

Conclusion: In developing countries like ours, anaemia during pregnancy is the most prevalent disease. The most common cause of this is nutritional deficiency. The disease is associated with high fetal and maternal complications, so care is strongly recommended for early diagnosis to improve maternal and fetal health.

Keywords: iron supplementations, iron stores, fetus, Iron deficiency anaemia

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INTRODUCTION:

Half of the pregnant women worldwide suffer from anaemia, according to a United Nations report (UN). In South Asia, 75 per cent of pregnant women suffer from anaemia, while the rest only has 18 per cent. In pregnancy, WHO described anemia as Hb below 11g/dL and further graded it as mild (10.0-10.99 g/dL), moderate (7.0-9.9 g/dL) and extreme (<7.0 g/dL) anemia. Iron deficiency anaemia is the leading cause of anaemia in pregnancy and childbearing age estimated to be about 50 per cent, whereas iron deficiency anaemia is about 40 per cent to 88 per cent in developing countries. There is a reduction in body iron stores in pregnancy, increased red blood cell mass, and an increased need for iron induces iron deficiency in pregnancy. Some predisposing factors are multi-parity, late booking, low socioeconomic conditions, malaria infection, HIV infections and insufficient child spacing. Even after cost-effective prevention and treatment in our country, anaemia during pregnancy is extremely prevalent. The big dilemma behind anaemia during pregnancy is low socioeconomic status. The most common

complication of pregnancy, anaemia, should be identified early and treated accordingly. The prevalence of anaemia among pregnant women is, therefore, the main target of this research.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The current cross-sectional research was performed to determine the prevalence of anaemia in pregnancy in women 18-42 years of age. This research included 500 pregnant women in the active phase of labour at the Lahore Jinnah Hospital. Their finger stick test was performed to determine their levels of haemoglobin. Pregnant women below 18 years of age and above 42 years of age were excluded from this review. Informed consent was obtained, and the study's intent was given. The highest priority was protecting patient confidentiality.

RESULTS:

The research included 500 pregnant ladies between the ages of 18-42. The following frequencies and percentages were determined based on the WHO classification of anaemia in pregnancy:

Hemoglobin	Frequency	Percent
11g/dl (non-anemia)	243	48.6
10-10.9g/dl (mild anemia)	126	25.2
7-9.9g/dl(moderate anemia)	110	22.0
<7g/dl (severe anemia)	21	4.2
Results	500	100

There was normal haemoglobin in a total of 243 women. In comparison, 21 females had less than 7g/dl of haemoglobin. One hundred ten had severe anaemia, while 126 had mild anaemia. Also, cross-tabulation of age vs haemoglobin is developed to evaluate which type of anaemia is more prevalent among particular age groups, as follows:

Age	Hemoglobin				Total
	11g/dl	10-10.9d/dl	7-9.9g/dl	<7g/dl	
18-22	62	30	32	3	126
23-27	81	50	38	9	178
28-32	67	33	29	8	137
33-37	26	9	8	1	44
38-42	7	4	3	0	14
Total	243	125	110	21	500

A total of 81 females aged 23-27 had 11mg/dl of haemoglobin. On the other hand, only seven females between the ages of 38-42 had 11 mg/dl haemoglobin levels. None of the women over the age of 38 had moderate anaemia, while nine women had severe anaemia, the largest between the ages of 23 and 27.

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence of anaemia in this study was high among pregnant women. For treatment, necessary blood tests such as complete blood image, serum iron and ferritin should be used to substitute iron with iron preparation via dietary modifications. The use of iron supplements and special treatment during breastfeeding is strongly recommended in order to prevent anaemia. More studies should be carried out on the risks of anaemia during pregnancy to reinforce all these results.

Recommendations:

In pregnancy, proper diet should be taken to prevent anaemia and diagnosis made by simple tests such as CBC should be taken seriously, and all possible treatments should be undertaken to avoid dire side effects.

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